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Phytochemical Study of *Rumex acetosa* Linn.

P. N. VARMA, D. R. LOHAR and A. K. SATSANGI

Homoeopathic Pharmacopoeia Laboratory,
Ghaziabad-201 002Manuscript received 22 September 1981, revised 18
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RUMEX acetosa Linn. (Polygonaceae) has been investigated earlier and oxalic, fumaric, α -ketoglutaric, succinic, glycolic, aconitic, citric and isocitric acids, napsoid, a naphthalene glucoside², chrysophanic acid, chrysophanein have been isolated^{3,4}. We have reinvestigated the chemical constituents of the leaves, since these are used in homoeopathy.

Powdered leaves (50 g) were soaked in 60% ethanol (500 ml) for 24 hr. The alcohol was decanted and the solvent removed. The remaining concentrate, thus obtained, was extracted with chloroform (25 ml \times 3). The chloroform extract (A) was concentrated on water bath to 10 ml. To the aqueous layer, sulphuric acid (6 N; 50 ml) was added and refluxed for 30 min. After cooling, it was again extracted with chloroform (25 ml \times 3). The chloroform extract (B) was also concentrated to 10 ml. This was washed with distilled water (25 \times 2 ml) and the acid free chloroform layer was chromatographed.

The chloroform extracts A and B were chromatographed over silica gel G plate (200 μ ; 10 \times 20 cm) using benzene-ethyl acetate (8 : 2 v/v) as solvent. The plates were sprayed with 0.5% methanolic magnesium acetate. Three pink coloured spots appeared at R_f 0.60, 0.75 and 0.98 in case of the extract 'A'.

The three yellow coloured compounds were isolated from chloroform extract A by preparative thin layer chromatography on silica gel G and were characterized as chrysophanol, 1,8-dihydroxy anthraquinone and 1,8-dihydroxy 3-hydroxymethyl anthra-

quinone (aloe-emodin), respectively by comparison with the data (uv, ir) available in literature^{5,6}.

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Chemical Constituents of *Physalis peruviana* RootsMAHENDRA SAHAI* and PARTHA NEOGI¹Department of Organic Chemistry, The Weizmann Institute
of Science, Rehovot, IsraelManuscript received 23 October 1982, accepted
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PHYSALIS peruviana Linn. (Solanaceae) is cultivated throughout India for its edible berries¹. The plant finds a variety of medicinal use in traditional system of medicine². The leaves of this plant yielded a number of withanolides³⁻⁷, physalin A⁸, perulactone⁹ and perulactone B⁹ while its roots yielded several new withanolides^{6,10} and tropane and secotropane alkaloids¹¹⁻¹⁴. The present communication reports the isolation of β -sitosterol, physalolactone, 4 β -hydroxywithanolide E, β -sitosterol-D-glucoside and rutin from the roots of this plant.

Experimental

Air-dried and powdered roots (2 kg) of *P. peruviana* were extracted with ethanol (95%). The ethanol extract was concentrated (1.0 l) and diluted with equal volume of water and then extracted successively with petrol (60-80°) and diethyl ether. The ether extract was washed with water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate, evaporated to dryness and chromatographed over silica gel column.

Results and Discussion

β -Sitosterol : Elution of the column with benzene yielded β -sitosterol, shining needles, m.p. 136°

*Department of Medicinal Chemistry, Institute of Medical Sciences, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi.

(MeOH), showed positive Libermann-Burchard test for steroids; acetate ($\text{Ac}_2\text{O}/\text{Et}_3\text{N}$), m.p. 124° ; identical (m.m.p. and co-tlc) with authentic sample.

Physalolactone: Elution of the above column with benzene-ethyl acetate (3:2) and repeated crystallization of the eluate yielded physalolactone, $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{38}\text{O}_8\text{Cl}$ (M^+ 538/540), m.p. $227-229^\circ$ (MeOH); monoacetate, m.p. $211-213^\circ$. Its identity with physalolactone was settled by direct comparison of two compounds, in view of their physical (m.m.p.) and physico-chemical (ir, uv and nmr) properties.

4 β -Hydroxywithanolide E: Elution of the above column with benzene-ethyl acetate (2:3), and crystallization of the eluates with ethyl acetate yielded 4 β -hydroxywithanolide E, $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{38}\text{O}_8$ (M^+ 502), m.p. 197° ; monoacetate, $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{40}\text{O}_9$ (M^+ 544). Its identity with 4 β -hydroxywithanolide E was settled by direct comparison of their physical and physico-chemical properties with authentic sample.

β -Sitosterol-D-glucoside: Elution of the column with ethyl acetate yielded β -sitosterol-D-glucoside, m.p. $288-289^\circ$ (MeOH); tetracetate ($\text{Ac}_2\text{O}/\text{Et}_3\text{N}$), m.p. $166-167^\circ$. Acid hydrolysis furnished β -sitosterol (m.m.p. and co-tlc) and D-glucose (co-paper chromatography). Identity of both the compounds were established by direct comparison (m.m.p. and co-tlc).

Rutin: The aqueous alcohol left after ethereal extraction, when kept at 4° for 7 days, deposited a yellow coloured amorphous powder which was crystallized from water as yellow needles, m.p. $188-190^\circ$, R_f 0.43 (BuOH-AcOH- H_2O : 4-1-5). Flavonoid nature of the compound was determined by its uv spectrum (λ_{max} 258 and 360 nm) and colour reactions (intense green colour with ferric chloride and positive Shinoda test). Acid hydrolysis of this compound furnished quercetin, $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_7$, m.p. 312° (m.m.p. and co-tlc) and glucose and rhamnose (co-paper chromatography). It furnished a decamethyl ether [α] -31° (EtOH) and was identified by direct comparison with an authentic sample of rutin.

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Biflavones in the Leaves of *Juniperus virginiana*

S. K. ROY, M. A. QASIM, M. KAMIL, N. ILYAS, M. ILYAS
and

WASIUR RAHMAN

Department of Chemistry, Aligarh Muslim University,
Aligath-202 031

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IN continuation of our interest in the biflavonyl pigments of Cupressaceae¹⁻⁵ we report the isolation of agathisflavone (Ia), cupressuflavone, amento-flavone, hinokiflavone (II) and isocryptomerin (IIa) from *Juniperus virginiana*. This constitutes the first example of occurrence and isolation of agathisflavone from *Juniperus* plants.

The pharmaceutical preparations of *Juniperus* are used for the treatment of hypertension and also as hypnotic⁶. Besides fungicidal and bacterial properties, *Juniperus virginiana* is reported to possess abortifacient activity⁷. Oils from the leaves and shoots are used in medicine. They have powerful diuretic properties⁸.

Experimental

Dried leaves (2 kg), collected from botanical gardens (Ooty), were extracted exhaustively with petroleum ether, benzene, ethylacetate and finally with acetone. The last two fractions were mixed and concentrated, and column chromatography over silica gel using benzene-ethylacetate in different ratio afforded several fractions. The last three fractions gave positive colour tests for flavonoids. They were mixed, concentrated and subjected to preparative tlc using benzene-pyridine-formic acid (36:9:5)⁹ as developer. This resolved it into three bands as JVI, JVII and JVIII in order of increasing R_f values.

JVI was found, on complete methylation followed by tlc, to be a mixture of four methylethers labelled